

Gravity from Invariance Under Transformations of Minkowski Metric

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Abstract

Minkowski manifold serves as the standard model of spacetime for relativistic theories of non-gravitating matter. It admits global coordinate systems and a Minkowski metric. In fact, it admits more than one Minkowski metric. In special relativity, one of these metrics is chosen as the non-dynamical physical metric. The theory is not invariant under transformations that map this metric to another Minkowski metric. We reformulate special relativity to make it invariant under such transformations by introducing a non-dynamical auxiliary tensor field. When we promote this field to be a dynamical gravitational field, it induces a dynamical physical metric. In order to determine the dynamics of this field, we propose an invariance principle, the principle of η -Covariance, which posits that any theory set on a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold must be independent of the choice of Minkowski metric. We construct a three-parameter theory of gravity which obeys this principle of η -Covariance. One specific choice of the three parameters yields the Einstein field equations. The action functional and the field equations of the theory are identical to the ones in New General Relativity, the theory of teleparallel gravity. In addition, the theory admits (i) the traceless canonical energy-momentum tensor of the gravitational field, (ii) the divergenceless total canonical energy-momentum tensor, (iii) the divergenceless total energy current vector and total momentum current vectors and (iv) the conserved total energy and total momentum. All these quantities are independent of the choice of Minkowski metric. The theory also admits the symmetric, divergenceless total energy-momentum tensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Special relativity lacks a dynamical physical metric. The spacetime in this theory is modelled by Minkowski manifold $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{\alpha\beta})$ on which the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ is represented by the non-dynamical Minkowski metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, i.e., $g_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta}$. Even in the presence of matter, $g_{\alpha\beta}$ remains unchanged. This non-dynamical nature of the physical metric is the reason why there is no consistent, experimentally verified special relativistic theory of gravity. Gravity is universal; it affects (and is affected by) everything in the universe, including the measuring devices. Therefore, the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$, that determines spacetime measurements, must

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be a dynamical physical quantity in a theory of gravitation.

In order to incorporate gravity, we must modify special relativity by decoupling $g_{\alpha\beta}$ from $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$. In such a modified theory, the underlying spacetime manifold may not be Minkowski; it may not even admit global charts or flat Lorentz metrics.

One possible modification is to altogether abandon Minkowski manifold as the model of spacetime in favour of a more general Lorentz manifold $(\mathbb{M}, g_{\alpha\beta})$ with the Lorentz metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ representing the dynamical physical metric. General Relativity and various other metric theories do exactly that.[1] These theories do not require the spacetime to admit global charts or flat metrics.

A milder modification is to represent spacetime by a bimetric Lorentz manifold $(\mathbb{M}, \eta_{\alpha\beta}, g_{\alpha\beta})$ equipped with a flat Lorentz metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ along with a Lorentz metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ representing the dynamical physical metric. This approach leads to various bimetric theories of gravitation.[2–5] These theories do not require the spacetime to admit global charts. One advantage of retaining the flat metric is that it allows for definition of conserved total energy-momentum tensor.

A still milder modification is to consider Minkowski manifold itself (or a nonempty open subset of it) as the model of spacetime and represent gravity using tensor fields that in turn induce a dynamical physical metric.[6] In this paper, we propose one such theory in which we represent gravity using a dynamical tensor field $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ on a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold. The physical metric is the ‘square’ of this field, viz. $g_{\alpha\beta} = h^\mu{}_\alpha \eta_{\mu\nu} h^\nu{}_\beta$. We assume that the theory obeys an invariance principle referred to as η -Covariance.¹ This principle exploits the fact that a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold admits multiple global charts and hence multiple Minkowski metrics. It states that any theory set on a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold must be independent of the choice of Minkowski metric. Specifically, its action must remain invariant if we replace the Minkowski metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ in it by another $\eta_{1\alpha\beta}$.

¹ We use the term *invariance principle* in the following sense:

A theory of physics obeys an invariance principle if the action functional remains invariant under certain stipulated transformations of the dynamical/non-dynamical fields/parameters of the theory.

General covariance and Poincaré Invariance are examples of an invariance principle. We restrict our discussion to theories based on an action principle. This includes all the established theories of the

All Minkowski metrics are related to one another by transformations that preserve flatness. In section II, we show that these transformations are generated by vector fields χ^α that are constructed from the global charts. In section III, we explore the role of these Minkowski metrics in special relativity. We also revisit some invariance principles obeyed by the theory. In section IV, we present the principle of η -Covariance and reformulate special relativity to make it η -Covariant. We then discuss how we can modify special relativity in order to incorporate gravity in a generally covariant and η -Covariant manner. In section V, we present a 3-parameter family of theories of gravity by introducing an η -Covariant action on a spacetime modelled by a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold. We show that one particular choice of the 3 parameters yields the Einstein field equations. Moreover, we show that the Lagrangian density and corresponding field equations of h^α_β are identical to the ones in New General Relativity, the theory of teleparallel gravity. In section VI, we define the η -Covariant total energy-momentum currents as well as the η -Covariant, conserved total energy and total momentum. Finally in section VII, we discuss some consequences of the theory.

II. GLOBAL CHARTS AND MINKOWSKI METRICS

One prominent feature of Minkowski manifold $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{\alpha\beta})$ is that it is equipped with global charts; the identity chart $\text{id}: \mathbb{R}^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4$ is the trivial example. However, it is not the only manifold with global charts. A nonempty open subset $\mathbb{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^4$ is also a manifold with global charts.² \mathbb{M} inherits these global charts from the (global as well as local) charts of \mathbb{R}^4 . Particularly, \mathbb{M} inherits its identity chart $\text{id}: M \rightarrow M$ from the one mentioned above.³ As an example, the open subset $\mathbb{R}^4 \setminus \{0\}$ is a manifold with global charts and its identity chart is given by (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3) with $-\infty < x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3 < \infty; (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3) \neq (0, 0, 0, 0)$.

Along with the global charts, \mathbb{M} inherits Minkowski metric as well from Minkowski manifold.⁴ In the identity chart $x^\alpha = (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3)$ of \mathbb{M} , the inherited metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ on \mathbb{M} has the canonical form $\eta_{\alpha\beta}(x) = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$.^{5,6} This canonical form reflects the fact that

fundamental forces.

² \mathbb{M} inherits its topology and differential structure from \mathbb{R}^4 .

³ We use the same notation (id) for both the identity chart on \mathbb{R}^4 and its restriction to \mathbb{M} without loss of clarity.

⁴ We refer to this inherited flat Lorentz metric as a Minkowski metric on \mathbb{M} . Usually Minkowski metric is

all the coordinates of the identity chart have identical units.⁷ We refer to the chart x^α as a Minkowski chart of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$.⁸

Let $x_1^{\alpha'} = (x_1^0, x_1^1, x_1^2, x_1^3)$ be another global chart on \mathbb{M} such that its coordinates have the same units as x^α . There exists a Minkowski metric $\eta_{1\alpha\beta}$ on \mathbb{M} given by the canonical form $\eta_{1\alpha'\beta'}(x_1) = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$ in $x_1^{\alpha'}$. In other words, $x_1^{\alpha'}$ is a Minkowski chart of $\eta_{1\alpha\beta}$. The components of $\eta_{1\alpha\beta}$ in x^α are:

$$\eta_{1\alpha\beta} = \frac{\partial x_1^{\alpha'}}{\partial x^\alpha} \eta_{1\alpha'\beta'} \frac{\partial x_1^{\beta'}}{\partial x^\beta} = J_\alpha^{\alpha'} \eta_{1\alpha'\beta'} J_\beta^{\beta'} \quad (1)$$

where $J_\alpha^{\alpha'}$ is the Jacobian matrix of the coordinate transformation $x_1^{\alpha'}(x)$.

If $\eta_{1\alpha\beta} \neq \eta_{\alpha\beta}$, then $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ and $\eta_{1\alpha\beta}$ are two distinct Minkowski metrics on \mathbb{M} and the coordinate transformation is not Poincaré transformation. Next, we derive the relationship between these two metrics.

Since the transformation $x_1^{\alpha'}(x)$ is defined everywhere on \mathbb{M} , we use it to construct a vector field χ_{10}^α on \mathbb{M} with components in chart x^α given by,

$$\chi_{10}^\alpha(x) = (x_1^0(x), x_1^1(x), x_1^2(x), x_1^3(x)) \quad (2)$$

Its covariant derivative with respect to $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ in chart x^α is,

$$\chi_{10}^\alpha{}_{;\beta} = \frac{\partial \chi_{10}^\alpha}{\partial x^\beta}$$

(We use colon to denote covariant derivative with respect to $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$.) Observe that the matrix of $\chi_{10}^\alpha{}_{;\beta}$ in x^α is the same as the Jacobian matrix $J_\alpha^{\alpha'}$. In addition, the matrix $\eta_{1\alpha'\beta'}$ is

defined as a flat Lorentz metric on Minkowski manifold. However, in this paper, we expand the scope of this definition to nonempty open subsets of \mathbb{R}^4 :

A flat Lorentz metric on a nonempty open subset of Minkowski spacetime $\mathbb{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^4$ is called a Minkowski metric.

⁵ Again, without loss of clarity, we use the same notation $(\eta_{\alpha\beta})$ for both a Minkowski metric on \mathbb{R}^4 and its restriction to \mathbb{M} .

⁶ We use sign convention of MTW.

⁷ We use natural units with $c = 1$ so that both the space and time measurements have same units.

⁸ A Minkowski chart of a Minkowski metric is a global chart in which the Minkowski metric has the canonical form $\text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$.

numerically the same as the matrix $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$. Therefore, we can construct a tensor equation which, in x^α , is mathematically the same as (1),

$$\eta_{\lambda\alpha\beta} = \chi_{10}{}^\mu{}_{:\alpha} \eta_{\mu\nu} \chi_{10}{}^\nu{}_{:\beta} \quad (3)$$

We refer to this transformation between the two Minkowski metrics as η -transformation. Since $J_\alpha^{\alpha'}$ is invertible everywhere on \mathbb{M} , so is $\chi_{10}{}^\alpha{}_{:\beta}$. Therefore, we can invert the equation (3),

$$\bar{\eta}_1{}^{\alpha\beta} = \bar{\chi}_{10}{}^\alpha{}_{\mu} \bar{\eta}^{\mu\nu} \bar{\chi}_{10}{}^\beta{}_{\nu} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\chi}_{10}{}^\alpha{}_{\beta}$ and $\bar{\eta}^{\alpha\beta}$ are inverses of $\chi_{10}{}^\alpha{}_{:\beta}$ and $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ respectively,⁹ that is,

$$\bar{\chi}_{10}{}^\alpha{}_{\gamma} \chi_{10}{}^\gamma{}_{:\beta} = \bar{\chi}_{10}{}^\gamma{}_{\beta} \chi_{10}{}^\alpha{}_{:\gamma} = \delta_\beta^\alpha$$

and

$$\bar{\eta}^{\alpha\gamma} \eta_{\gamma\beta} = \delta_\beta^\alpha$$

In general, consider two global charts $x_i{}^\alpha$ and $x_j{}^{\alpha'}$ on \mathbb{M} such that their coordinates have the same units as the identity chart. There exist two Minkowski metrics $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}$ and $\eta_{j\alpha\beta}$ on \mathbb{M} with components $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}(x_i) = \eta_{j\alpha'\beta'}(x_j) = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$. If the two metrics are distinct, that is, $\eta_{i\alpha\beta} \neq \eta_{j\alpha\beta}$, then they are related to each other by η -transformations,

$$\eta_{j\alpha\beta} = \chi_{ji}{}^\mu{}_{\uparrow\alpha} \eta_{i\mu\nu} \chi_{ji}{}^\nu{}_{\uparrow\beta} \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{i\alpha\beta} = \chi_{ij}{}^\mu{}_{\downarrow\alpha} \eta_{j\mu\nu} \chi_{ij}{}^\nu{}_{\downarrow\beta} \quad (6)$$

where the vector fields $\chi_{ji}{}^\mu$ and $\chi_{ij}{}^\mu$ are constructed from the coordinate transformations $x_j{}^{\alpha'}(x_i)$ and $x_i{}^\alpha(x_j)$ respectively as in (2). \uparrow and \downarrow denote covariant derivatives with respect to $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}$ and $\eta_{j\alpha\beta}$ respectively. These covariant derivatives are inverses of each other,

$$\bar{\chi}_{ij}{}^\mu{}_{\nu} = \chi_{ji}{}^\mu{}_{\uparrow\nu}$$

$$\bar{\chi}_{ji}{}^\mu{}_{\nu} = \chi_{ij}{}^\mu{}_{\downarrow\nu}$$

Thus, the existence of global charts on a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold $\mathbb{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^4$ guarantees the existence of multiple Minkowski metrics on \mathbb{M} that are related to each other by equations of type (5) and (6).

⁹ We denote the inverse of an invertible tensor X by a bar \bar{X} . However, as the only exception, we denote the inverse of $g_{\alpha\beta}$ by $g^{\alpha\beta}$ without ambiguity.

Let us now explore the special case when $\eta_{1\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta}$, that is, when the coordinate transformation $x_1^{\alpha'}(x)$ is a Poincaré transformation, a (passive) isometry of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$. As in case of equation (2), we use this transformation to construct a vector field $P^{\eta_{10}^\alpha}$ on \mathbb{M} with components in chart x^α given by,

$$P^{\eta_{10}^\alpha}(x) = (x_1^0(x), x_1^1(x), x_1^2(x), x_1^3(x)) \quad (7)$$

The superscript η of $P^{\eta_{10}^\alpha}$ highlights the fact that the vector field is constructed from a (passive) isometry of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$.

Following the arguments that led to the equations (3) and (4), we obtain the metric preserving η -transformations,

$$\eta_{\alpha\beta} = P^{\eta_{10}^\mu}_{:\alpha} \eta_{\mu\nu} P^{\eta_{10}^\nu}_{:\beta} \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{\eta}^{\alpha\beta} = \bar{P}^{\eta_{10}^\alpha}_{\mu} \bar{\eta}^{\mu\nu} \bar{P}^{\eta_{10}^\beta}_{\nu} \quad (9)$$

Note that the matrix of $P^{\eta_{10}^\alpha}_{:\beta}$ in x^α is equal to the constant Lorentz matrix Λ of the global transformation $x_1^{\alpha'}(x)$ and therefore, $P^{\eta_{10}^\alpha}_{:\beta}$ is covariantly constant, $P^{\eta_{10}^\alpha}_{:\beta\gamma} = 0$.

In general, consider a global chart x_{i0}^α on \mathbb{M} such that its coordinates have the same units as the identity chart. There exists a Minkowski metric $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}$ on \mathbb{M} with components $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}(x_{i0}) = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$. Consider another global chart $x_{i1}^{\alpha'}$ related to the first by the Poincaré transformation $x_{i1}^{\alpha'}(x_{i0})$. In short, both x_{i0}^α and $x_{i1}^{\alpha'}$ are Minkowski charts of $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}$. Then the corresponding metric preserving η -transformations are

$$\eta_{i\alpha\beta} = P^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}_{\uparrow\alpha} \eta_{i\mu\nu} P^{\eta_{i0}^\nu}_{\uparrow\beta} \quad (10)$$

$$\eta_{i\alpha\beta} = P^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}_{\uparrow\alpha} \eta_{i\mu\nu} P^{\eta_{i0}^\nu}_{\uparrow\beta} \quad (11)$$

where the vector fields $P^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}$ and $P^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}$ are constructed from the Poincaré transformations $x_{i1}^{\alpha'}(x_{i0})$ and $x_{i0}^\alpha(x_{i1})$ respectively as in (7). Their covariant derivatives are inverses of each other,

$$\bar{P}^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}_{\nu} = P^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}_{\uparrow\nu}$$

$$\bar{P}^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}_{\nu} = P^{\eta_{i0}^\mu}_{\uparrow\nu}$$

These covariant derivatives are covariantly constant, $P^{\eta_{i0}^\alpha}_{\uparrow\beta\gamma} = P^{\eta_{i0}^\alpha}_{\uparrow\beta\gamma} = 0$.

Observe that equation (8) is not the most general tensorial congruence relation that preserves the metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$. The general relation is given in terms of an invertible tensor field

$L^\eta{}^\alpha{}_\beta$:

$$\eta_{\alpha\beta} = L^\eta{}^\mu{}_\alpha \eta_{\mu\nu} L^\eta{}^\nu{}_\beta \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{\eta}^{\alpha\beta} = \bar{L}^\eta{}^\alpha{}_\mu \bar{\eta}^{\mu\nu} \bar{L}^\eta{}^\beta{}_\nu \quad (13)$$

where the components of $L^\eta{}^\alpha{}_\beta$ in a Minkowski chart x^α of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, at any spacetime point are equal to the components of a (local) Lorentz matrix.

The transformation (12) is not an η -transformation in general. It is one only if $L^\eta{}^\alpha{}_\beta = P^\alpha{}_{;\beta}$ for some vector field P^α .

III. SPECIAL RELATIVITY

Since the Minkowski manifold admits many Minkowski metrics, we need to explore their physical relevance. In special relativity, the identity chart $\text{id}: \mathbb{R}^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4$ is chosen to represent an inertial frame. This choice uniquely determines the Minkowski metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ to represent the physical metric.¹⁰

Once we choose a Minkowski metric to be the physical metric, we cannot use any other Minkowski metric as the physical metric. As an illustration, let us consider motion of free particles. The trajectories of free particles are given by geodesics of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ which are straight lines in an inertial frame. Geodesics of any other Minkowski metric $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}$ are different, in general, from those of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ and hence cannot represent trajectories of free particles. All observers, inertial or not, must use the same chosen Minkowski metric as the physical metric. All the other metrics are non-physical. Special relativity is a theory with a preferred metric.

This rigidity with respect to the choice of the physical metric means that special relativity is not diffeomorphism invariant. Under a diffeomorphism $\phi: \mathbb{R}^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4$, $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ generally transforms into a different Minkowski metric $\phi^*\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, so the theory fails to be diffeomorphism invariant in general. It remains invariant only when the diffeomorphism is an isometry ϕ_I , that is, $\phi_I^*\eta_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta}$. Such an isometry is simply an (active) Poincaré transformation and we say that special relativity is Poincaré invariant. Particularly, the action is Poincaré invariant: $S[\eta_{\alpha\beta}, \psi] = S[\eta_{\alpha\beta}, \phi_I^*\psi]$ where ψ denotes the collection of non-gravitational matter

¹⁰ The selection of the identity chart as an inertial frame is a convenient choice. We are free to choose any global chart $x_i{}^\alpha$ as an inertial frame. In that case the physical metric is represented by the corresponding Minkowski metric $\eta_{i\alpha\beta}$.

fields. Owing to Noether's first theorem, Poincaré invariance of the action leads to a conserved canonical energy-momentum tensor and a conserved angular momentum tensor when the equations of motion of the matter fields ψ are satisfied. Further, using the Belinfante procedure, we can obtain the symmetric, conserved Belinfante-Rosenfeld energy-momentum tensor.[7–9]

Special relativity is not generally covariant either. A spacetime theory of physics is generally covariant if the action is invariant under any general coordinate transformation. This is not the case with special relativity. However, we can reformulate the theory in a generally covariant form. In a general coordinate system, the metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ is not necessarily in its canonical form and its Levi-Civita connection can be nonzero. Therefore, in order to obtain the generally covariant formulation of special relativity, we replace all partial derivatives by covariant derivatives with respect to $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$. In this generally covariant special relativity, the action $S[\eta_{\alpha\beta}, \psi]$ is invariant under any general coordinate transformation. This formulation allows us to define the symmetric Hilbert tensor to be the functional derivative of the action,

$$T^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{|\eta|}} \frac{\delta S}{\delta \eta_{\alpha\beta}} \quad (14)$$

where $|\eta|$ is magnitude of the determinant of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ and $\delta\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ are functional variations of the components of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ induced by an infinitesimal coordinate transformation $x^\alpha \rightarrow x^\alpha + \delta x^\alpha$. Owing to Noether's second theorem, general covariance of the theory ensures that the Hilbert tensor is divergenceless provided the equations of motion of the matter fields ψ are satisfied. This symmetric, divergenceless Hilbert tensor coincides with the Belinfante-Rosenfeld tensor.

IV. η -COVARIANCE

In special relativity, the action is not invariant under η -transformation (3), that is, $S[\eta_{\alpha\beta}, \psi] \neq S[\eta_{1\alpha\beta}, \psi]$. However, we can reformulate the theory so that the action remains invariant under η -transformation without changing the physical metric! To begin with, we introduce a non-dynamical, auxiliary tensor field $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ related to the physical metric by,

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta} = h^\mu{}_\alpha \eta_{\mu\nu} h^\nu{}_\beta \quad (15)$$

so that

$$h^\mu{}_\alpha = P^\eta{}_{10}{}^\mu{}_{:\alpha} \quad (16)$$

where the vector field $P^{\eta}_{10}{}^{\mu}$ is defined in equation (7).

Along with the η -transformation (3), let h^{α}_{β} transform as,

$$h_1{}^{\gamma}{}_{\beta} = \bar{\chi}_{10}{}^{\gamma}{}_{\alpha} h^{\alpha}{}_{\beta} \quad (17)$$

Since h^{α}_{β} is invertible, the inverse transformation is,

$$\bar{h}_1{}^{\alpha}{}_{\gamma} = \chi_{10}{}^{\beta}{}_{\gamma} \bar{h}^{\alpha}{}_{\beta} \quad (18)$$

The metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ and its inverse remain invariant under the simultaneous transformations (3), (17) and (18),

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = h^{\mu}{}_{\alpha} \eta_{\mu\nu} h^{\nu}{}_{\beta} = h_1{}^{\mu}{}_{\alpha} \eta_{1\mu\nu} h_1{}^{\nu}{}_{\beta} \quad (19)$$

and

$$g^{\alpha\beta} = \bar{h}^{\alpha}{}_{\mu} \bar{\eta}^{\mu\nu} \bar{h}^{\beta}{}_{\nu} = \bar{h}_1{}^{\alpha}{}_{\mu} \bar{\eta}_1{}^{\mu\nu} \bar{h}_1{}^{\beta}{}_{\nu} \quad (20)$$

Thus, introducing the field h^{α}_{β} allows us to write the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ using any Minkowski metric.

Next, in the generally covariant special relativity, let the action be given by,

$$S = \int \mathcal{L}(g_{\alpha\beta}, \psi, \psi_{;\alpha}) d^4x \quad (21)$$

where the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} is assumed to be a function of the metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$, the matter fields ψ and their covariant derivatives with respect to $g_{\alpha\beta}$, $\psi_{;\alpha}$. (We use semicolon to denote covariant derivative with respect to $g_{\alpha\beta}$.) Note that in special relativity, $g_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta}$ and therefore, $\psi_{;\alpha} = \psi_{,\alpha}$. We assume that ψ remain invariant under the transformations (3) and (17). Then $\psi_{;\alpha}$ remain invariant as well since both ψ and $g_{\alpha\beta}$ are invariant under these transformations. As a result, \mathcal{L} , and hence S , remain invariant,

$$\mathcal{L}(g_{\alpha\beta}, \psi, \psi_{;\alpha}) = \mathcal{L}(\eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^{\alpha}{}_{\beta}, \psi, \psi_{;\alpha}) = \mathcal{L}(\eta_{1\alpha\beta}, h_1{}^{\alpha}{}_{\beta}, \psi, \psi_{;\alpha}) \quad (22)$$

In conclusion, any generally covariant special relativistic theory based on an action principle can be made invariant under η -transformation (3) by introducing a non-dynamical field h^{α}_{β} using the prescription (15) and transforming it according to (17).¹¹ We will refer to this invariance principle as η -Covariance. We will also expand the scope of this principle to any theory defined on a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold.

¹¹ This conclusion applies to every special relativistic theory based on an action principle even when it is not written in generally covariant form.

η -Covariance. Let the spacetime manifold $(\mathbb{M}, \eta_{\alpha\beta})$ be a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{\alpha\beta})$ with topology and differential structure inherited from \mathbb{R}^4 . Consider a spacetime theory defined by an action functional $S[\eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^\alpha{}_\beta, \psi]$ of fields $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ and ψ . If the action remains invariant under the transformations (3) and (17), then we say that the theory is η -Covariant.

For an η -Covariant theory, $S[\eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^\alpha{}_\beta, \psi] = S[\eta_{1\alpha\beta}, h_1{}^\alpha{}_\beta, \psi]$ and, in addition, the manifolds $(\mathbb{M}, \eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^\alpha{}_\beta, \psi)$ and $(\mathbb{M}, \eta_{1\alpha\beta}, h_1{}^\alpha{}_\beta, \psi)$ represent the same spacetime. In special relativity, the spacetime is represented by $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{\alpha\beta}, \psi)$ and not by $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{1\alpha\beta}, \psi)$. However, in the η -Covariant special relativity, both $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^\alpha{}_\beta, \psi)$ and $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{1\alpha\beta}, h_1{}^\alpha{}_\beta, \psi)$ represent the same spacetime.

We say that a quantity is η -Covariant if it remains invariant under the transformations (3) and (17). The action S , the metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ and the matter fields ψ are η -Covariant.

η -Covariance ensures that a theory is independent of the choice of Minkowski metric. It is analogous to general covariance which ensures that a theory is independent of the choice of coordinate system. This analogy is not perfect though; in a generally covariant theory, the Lagrangian density is an implicit function of coordinates whereas in an η -Covariant theory, the Lagrangian density may explicitly depend on $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ and/or $h^\alpha{}_\beta$. This is indeed the case with the theory we present in the next section.

In the η -Covariant special relativity, on the other hand, the Lagrangian density implicitly depends on $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ and $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ through relation (19). Since $g_{\alpha\beta}$ is η -Covariant, there are no Noether identities associated with η -Covariance of the theory.

In the next section, we modify the generally covariant and η -Covariant formulation of special relativity by promoting $h^\alpha{}_\beta$, and hence $g_{\alpha\beta}$, to be dynamical fields. Such a modification violates the Poincaré Invariance since a Poincaré transformation is not an isometry of a dynamical physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$. Instead, the equivalence principle requires that the modified theory obeys local Lorentz invariance which locally preserves the form of the physical metric.

V. THE THEORY

We begin with the assumption that the spacetime $(\mathbb{M}, \eta_{\alpha\beta})$ is a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{\alpha\beta})$. On this spacetime manifold, we formally introduce an invertible tensor field $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ to represent the gravitational field. We further assume that $h^\alpha{}_\beta$

induces the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ given by,

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = h^\mu{}_\alpha \eta_{\mu\nu} h^\nu{}_\beta \quad (23)$$

and therefore

$$g^{\alpha\beta} = \bar{h}^\alpha{}_\mu \bar{\eta}^{\mu\nu} \bar{h}^\beta{}_\nu \quad (24)$$

Being a gravitational field, $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ is different from $P^\eta{}_{10}{}^\alpha{}_\beta$ and $\chi_{10}{}^\alpha{}_\beta$ in general and therefore $g_{\alpha\beta}$ is not necessarily a Minkowski metric but instead a Lorentz metric with possibly nonzero curvature.

We assume that the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L}_h of the gravitational field is an η -Covariant function of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ and their first derivatives. In order to construct the Lagrangian density, we first define the η -Covariant gravitational field strength tensor:

$$\mathfrak{T}^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma} = \bar{h}^\alpha{}_\mu (h^\mu{}_{\beta:\gamma} - h^\mu{}_{\gamma:\beta}) \quad (25)$$

This tensor is the torsion tensor of an η -Covariant affine connection given by

$$\Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma} = \Gamma(\eta)^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma} + \bar{h}^\alpha{}_\mu h^\mu{}_{\beta:\gamma} \quad (26)$$

so that

$$\mathfrak{T}^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma} = \Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma} - \Gamma^\alpha{}_{\gamma\beta} \quad (27)$$

where $\Gamma(\eta)^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}$ is the Levi-Civita connection of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$. In Appendix A, we show that $\Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}$ is a Weitzenböck connection.

The most general η -Covariant and generally covariant action quadratic in $\mathfrak{T}^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}$ is,

$$\begin{aligned} S_h &= \frac{1}{16\pi G} \int \mathcal{L}_h(g_{\alpha\beta}, \mathfrak{T}^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}) d^4x \\ &= \frac{1}{16\pi G} \int \sqrt{|g|} (c_1 \mathfrak{T}^{\alpha\beta\gamma} \mathfrak{T}_{\alpha\beta\gamma} + c_2 \mathfrak{T}^{\alpha\beta\gamma} \mathfrak{T}_{\gamma\beta\alpha} + c_3 \mathfrak{T}^\alpha{}_{\beta\alpha} \mathfrak{T}^{\beta\gamma}{}_\gamma) d^4x \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where $|g|$ is magnitude of the determinant of metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ and c_1, c_2, c_3 are constant parameters. Tensor indices are raised and lowered using the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$.

Observe that $\mathfrak{T}^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}$ and therefore S_h vanish identically when $h^\alpha{}_\beta = P^\eta{}_{10}{}^\alpha{}_\beta$ or $\chi_{10}{}^\alpha{}_\beta$, that is, when $g_{\alpha\beta}$ is a Minkowski metric. This action is identical to the one in New General Relativity, the theory of teleparallel gravity.¹²

Let the action of the matter fields ψ be of the form,

$$S_\psi = \int \mathcal{L}_\psi(g_{\alpha\beta}, \psi, \psi_{;\alpha}) d^4x \quad (29)$$

¹² Note that the definition of torsion (equation 28) is opposite to the one used in teleparallel gravity.

Note that $\psi_{;\alpha} \neq \psi_{.\alpha}$ in general. We also assume that S_ψ obeys the equivalence principle: in a local inertial frame $x^{\hat{\alpha}}$ at a spacetime point Q with $g_{\hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta}}|_Q = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$ and $g_{\hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta},\hat{\gamma}}|_Q = 0$, $\mathcal{L}_\psi|_Q$ coincides with the corresponding Lagrangian density in special relativity. (We use comma to denote partial derivative.)

The total action is:

$$S = S_h + S_\psi \quad (30)$$

The Euler-Lagrange equations of $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ are:¹³

$$\frac{1}{16\pi G} \frac{1}{\sqrt{|g|}} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial h^\alpha{}_\beta} - \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial h^\alpha{}_{\beta;\gamma}} \right)_{;\gamma} \right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{|g|}} \frac{\delta \mathcal{L}_\psi}{\delta h^\alpha{}_\beta} = 0 \quad (31)$$

In order to write these field equations in the canonical form, we introduce four definitions:

1. The η -Covariant canonical superpotential:

$$\mathcal{S}_\alpha{}^{\beta\gamma} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|g|}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial \mathfrak{T}^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}} \quad (32)$$

2. The η -Covariant, traceless canonical energy-momentum tensor of the gravitational field:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{h\alpha}{}^\beta &= \frac{1}{16\pi G} \frac{1}{\sqrt{|g|}} h^\gamma{}_\alpha \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial h^\gamma{}_\beta} \\ &= \frac{1}{16\pi G} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{|g|}} \mathcal{L}_h \delta_\alpha^\beta - 2 \mathcal{S}_\mu{}^{\beta\gamma} \mathfrak{T}^\mu{}_{\alpha\gamma} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where δ_β^α is the identity tensor.

3. The η -Covariant, symmetric Hilbert tensor:

$$T^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{|g|}} \frac{\delta \mathcal{L}_\psi}{\delta g_{\alpha\beta}} \quad (34)$$

4. The η -Covariant total canonical energy-momentum tensor:

$$\mathcal{T}_\alpha{}^\beta = \mathcal{T}_{h\alpha}{}^\beta + T_\alpha{}^\beta \quad (35)$$

¹³ In calculating the two partial derivatives, we treat $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ and $h^\alpha{}_{\beta;\gamma}$ as independent variables. Therefore, $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial h^\alpha{}_\beta}$ is a tensor.

Using these definitions in field equations (31) we get,

$$(|h| \bar{h}^\mu{}_\alpha \mathcal{S}_\mu{}^{\beta\gamma})_{;\gamma} = 8\pi G |h| \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\alpha \mathcal{T}_\gamma{}^\beta \quad (36)$$

where the scalar field $|h|$ is magnitude of the determinant of $h^\alpha{}_\beta$. In a general coordinate system, these equations take the form,

$$\left(\sqrt{|g|} \mathcal{S}_\alpha{}^{\beta\gamma}\right)_{;\gamma} = 8\pi G \left(\frac{1}{16\pi G} \left(\mathcal{L}_h \delta_\alpha^\beta + 2 \sqrt{|g|} \mathcal{S}_\mu{}^{\beta\gamma} \Gamma^\mu{}_{\gamma\alpha}\right) + \sqrt{|g|} T_\alpha{}^\beta\right) \quad (37)$$

These equations are identical to the field equations of New General Relativity.¹⁴

We can rewrite the field equations (36) in an η -Covariant form:

$$\mathcal{G}^{\alpha\beta} = 8\pi G T^{\alpha\beta} \quad (38)$$

where the tensor $\mathcal{G}^{\alpha\beta}$ is η -Covariant. Owing to Noether's second theorem, general covariance of the matter action S_ψ implies that $T^{\alpha\beta}$ is divergenceless with respect to $g_{\alpha\beta}$ ($T^{\alpha\beta}{}_{;\beta} = 0$) when the matter fields ψ obey their respective equations of motion. $\mathcal{G}^{\alpha\beta}$, however, is neither symmetric nor divergenceless in general. Therefore we split the field equations (38) into symmetric and antisymmetric parts,

$$\mathcal{G}^{(\alpha\beta)} = 8\pi G T^{\alpha\beta} \quad (39)$$

$$\mathcal{G}^{[\alpha\beta]} = 0 \quad (40)$$

constrained by,
$$\mathcal{G}^{(\alpha\beta)}{}_{;\beta} = 0 \quad (41)$$

In the special case $(c_1, c_2, c_3) = (-\frac{1}{4}, -\frac{1}{2}, 1)$,¹⁵ the tensor $\mathcal{G}^{\alpha\beta}$ becomes equal to the Einstein tensor $G^{\alpha\beta}$ and equation (38) simplifies to the Einstein's equation,

$$G^{\alpha\beta} = 8\pi G T^{\alpha\beta} \quad (42)$$

¹⁴ Note that the definitions (32), (33) and (34) are opposite to the ones used in teleparallel gravity.

¹⁵ Values of c_1, c_2, c_3 are opposite to the ones in New General Relativity due to the use of opposite sign conventions.^{12, 14, 6}

VI. ENERGY MOMENTUM CONSERVATION

η -Covariance and general covariance of S_h ensures that the canonical superpotential $\mathcal{S}_\alpha^{\beta\gamma}$ is antisymmetric in (β, γ) and therefore the left hand side of field equations (36) is divergenceless:

$$(|h| \bar{h}^\mu{}_\alpha \mathcal{S}_\mu^{\beta\gamma})_{;\gamma\beta} = 0 \quad (43)$$

and so is the right hand side,

$$(|h| \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\alpha \mathcal{T}_\gamma^\beta)_{;\beta} = 0 \quad (44)$$

This vanishing covariant divergence allows us to define η -Covariant conserved charges under suitable boundary conditions as we see next.

Let $\xi_{(\mu)}^\alpha$ be the four spacetime-translation Killing fields of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ where $\mu \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. We use these Killing fields to define the four η -Covariant currents, the total canonical energy current and the three total canonical momentum currents:

$$J_{(\mu)}^\alpha = \xi_{(\mu)}^\gamma \bar{h}^\beta{}_\gamma \mathcal{T}_\beta^\alpha \quad (45)$$

We can express this definition in terms of the canonical superpotential using the field equations (36) and the identity $\xi_{(\mu)}^\alpha{}_{;\beta} = 0$:

$$J_{(\mu)}^\alpha = \frac{1}{8\pi G} \frac{1}{|h|} (|h| \xi_{(\mu)}^\nu \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\nu \mathcal{S}_\gamma^{\alpha\beta})_{;\beta} \quad (46)$$

The right hand side is antisymmetric in (α, β) . Therefore, with the help of the identity $\sqrt{|g|} = \sqrt{|\eta|} |h|$ we can re-express this definition as a divergence of an antisymmetric tensor field with respect to the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$:

$$J_{(\mu)}^\alpha = \frac{1}{8\pi G} (\xi_{(\mu)}^\nu \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\nu \mathcal{S}_\gamma^{\alpha\beta})_{;\beta} \quad (47)$$

Due to antisymmetry, the right hand side satisfies the condition

$$(\xi_{(\mu)}^\nu \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\nu \mathcal{S}_\gamma^{\alpha\beta})_{;\beta\alpha} = 0 \quad (48)$$

Therefore, the four currents are divergenceless as well:

$$J_{(\mu)}^\alpha{}_{;\alpha} = 0 \quad (49)$$

Owing to Gauss's divergence theorem, these divergenceless currents imply existence of four conserved charges under appropriate boundary conditions. These η -Covariant charges passing through a hypersurface Σ are defined as

$$P_\mu = - \int_{\Sigma} J_{(\mu)}^\alpha d\Sigma_\alpha \quad (50)$$

where the directed volume element $d\Sigma_\alpha$ on the hypersurface is induced by the spacetime volume element $\sqrt{|g|}d^4x$. Using the definition (45) and the equation (47), we get

$$P_\mu = - \int_{\Sigma} \xi_{(\mu)}^\gamma \bar{h}^\beta{}_\gamma \mathcal{T}_\beta{}^\alpha d\Sigma_\alpha \quad (51)$$

$$= - \frac{1}{8\pi G} \int_{\Sigma} (\xi_{(\mu)}^\nu \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\nu \mathcal{S}_\gamma{}^{\alpha\beta})_{;\beta} d\Sigma_\alpha \quad (52)$$

The integrand here is a divergence of an antisymmetric tensor field. Therefore, we apply Gauss's divergence theorem to obtain

$$P_\mu = - \frac{1}{8\pi G} \oint_{\partial\Sigma} \xi_{(\mu)}^\nu \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\nu \mathcal{S}_\gamma{}^{\alpha\beta} d\Omega_{\alpha\beta} \quad (53)$$

where the integral is over the boundary surface $\partial\Sigma$ of Σ and the directed surface element $d\Omega_{\alpha\beta}$ is induced by the hypersurface volume element $d\Sigma_\alpha$.

If the hypersurface Σ is non-null with respect to the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ then we can write the integrals in equations (50) and (51) using a coordinate system (t, x^i) in which x^i are coordinates on Σ . If n^α is the unit normal to Σ ($n^\alpha n_\alpha = \pm 1$) and σ_{ij} is the metric on Σ induced by $g_{\alpha\beta}$, then

$$P_\mu = - \int_{\Sigma} J_{(\mu)}^\alpha n_\alpha \sqrt{|\sigma|} d^3x \quad (54)$$

$$= - \int_{\Sigma} \xi_{(\mu)}^\gamma \bar{h}^\beta{}_\gamma \mathcal{T}_\beta{}^\alpha n_\alpha \sqrt{|\sigma|} d^3x \quad (55)$$

where $|\sigma|$ is magnitude of the determinant of σ_{ij} . Similarly, if the boundary $\partial\Sigma$ is non-null, then we can write the integral in equation (53) as

$$P_\mu = - \frac{1}{8\pi G} \oint_{\partial\Sigma} \xi_{(\mu)}^\nu \bar{h}^\gamma{}_\nu \mathcal{S}_\gamma{}^{\alpha\beta} n_\alpha m_\beta \sqrt{|\omega|} d^2y \quad (56)$$

where y^a are coordinates on $\partial\Sigma$, ω_{ab} is the metric on $\partial\Sigma$ induced by σ_{ij} , $|\omega|$ is magnitude of the determinant of ω_{ab} and m^α is the unit normal to $\partial\Sigma$ ($m^\alpha m_\alpha = \pm 1$).

If the hypersurface Σ is spacelike, then P_0 is the total energy and P_i is the total momentum passing through it. In this case, if the coordinates (t, x^i) are Gaussian normal coordinates,

then these four charges P_μ are conserved (i.e., time independent) provided the net flux of the corresponding currents $J_{(\mu)}^i$ through the boundary $\partial\Sigma$ is zero.

η -Covariance ensures that $J_{(\mu)}^\alpha$ and P_μ are independent of the choice of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ and its Killing fields $\xi_{(\mu)}^\alpha$.

The canonical total energy-momentum tensor \mathcal{T}_α^β is not symmetric. However, η -Covariance of the theory leads us to a symmetric, divergenceless total energy-momentum tensor. We define this symmetric total energy-momentum tensor as:

$$\mathcal{T}^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{|\eta|}} \frac{\delta S}{\delta \eta_{\alpha\beta}} \quad (57)$$

where $\delta\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ is functional variation of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ induced by an infinitesimal η -transformation. Owing to Noether's second theorem, η -Covariance of the action leads to the following relations provided that the field equations (36) are satisfied:

$$\mathcal{S}^{(\alpha\beta)\gamma}{}_{;\gamma} = 8\pi G \mathcal{T}^{\alpha\beta} \quad (58)$$

$$\mathcal{S}^{[\alpha\beta]\gamma}{}_{;\gamma} = 0 \quad (59)$$

where the superpotential $\mathcal{S}^{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{S}^{\alpha\beta\gamma} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|\eta|}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \bar{\eta}^{\alpha\mu} h^\beta{}_\nu \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial h^\mu{}_{\nu,\gamma}} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial \eta_{\alpha\beta,\gamma}} \right) \quad (60)$$

$$= |h| h^\alpha{}_\mu h^\beta{}_\nu \mathcal{S}^{\mu\nu\gamma} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{|\eta|}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_h}{\partial \eta_{\alpha\beta,\gamma}} \quad (61)$$

Comparing equations (58) and (59) with equations (36) we see that the total energy-momentum tensor $\eta_{\alpha\gamma} \mathcal{T}^{\gamma\beta}$ differs from the total canonical energy-momentum tensor \mathcal{T}_α^β by divergence of an antisymmetric tensor.

η -Covariance of the action ensures that $\mathcal{S}^{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ is antisymmetric in (β, γ) . Therefore

$$\mathcal{S}^{\alpha\beta\gamma}{}_{;\gamma\beta} = 0 \quad (62)$$

As a result, the total energy-momentum tensor is divergenceless,

$$\mathcal{T}^{\alpha\beta}{}_{;\beta} = 0 \quad (63)$$

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Finally, we need to ascertain the possible values of parameters c_1, c_2, c_3 for which the theory agrees with observations. If we choose $(2c_1 + c_2, c_3) = (-1, 1)$, then the theory

reduces to the appropriate Newtonian limit (Appendix B). In fact, in this special case, the Schwarzschild metric is a solution for a static, isotropic spacetime (Appendix C) and the FLRW metric is a solution for a homogeneous, isotropic spacetime.

The Lagrangian density (28) and the field equations (37) of h^α_β in this theory are identical to the ones in New General Relativity. We ascribe this coincidence to the relationship between the tensorial gravitational field h^α_β and the cotetrad field e^a_β (Appendix A) as well as to the fact that the gravitational field strength tensor $\mathfrak{T}^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}$ is η -Covariant. As a result of this coincidence, the predictions given above match the corresponding predictions of New General Relativity.

Notwithstanding the coincidence, the two theories make different assumptions about the spacetime manifold. In New General Relativity, the spacetime is a Lorentz manifold with global tetrad fields whereas in this theory, the spacetime is a Lorentz manifold with global charts. In addition, New General Relativity is a gauge theory of translation group whereas this theory is based on the invariance principle of η -Covariance.

The advantage of this theory over New General Relativity is the existence of various energy-momentum tensors (33), (35), (57) as well as divergenceless vector currents (45) and corresponding conserved charges (50).

The dynamical nature of h^α_β ensures that the theory is diffeomorphism invariant. The action is invariant under diffeomorphism $\phi: \mathbb{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{M}; S[\eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^\alpha_\beta, \psi] = S[\phi^*\eta_{\alpha\beta}, \phi^*h^\alpha_\beta, \phi^*\psi]$. Both $(\mathbb{M}, \eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^\alpha_\beta, \psi)$ and $(\mathbb{M}, \phi^*\eta_{\alpha\beta}, \phi^*h^\alpha_\beta, \phi^*\psi)$ represent the same spacetime.

Appendix A: Weitzenböck Connection

In a Minkowski chart x^α of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, $\Gamma(\eta)^\alpha_{\beta\gamma} = 0$. Therefore in this chart, the affine connection (26) takes the form

$$\Gamma^\alpha_{\beta\gamma} = \bar{h}^\alpha_{\mu} h^\mu_{\beta,\gamma} \quad (\text{A1})$$

where comma denotes a partial derivative. This equation resembles the definition of a Weitzenböck connection in the Weitzenböck gauge (in which the spin connection is identically zero). In order to prove that $\Gamma^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}$ is Weitzenböck, we first construct a tetrad field from the gravitational field h^α_β as follows.

Since the spacetime manifold \mathbb{M} is assumed to be an open subset of Minkowski manifold, it is parallelizable and therefore, it admits global tetrad fields. Because h^α_β is globally

invertible, we can construct a tetrad field e_a^α and the corresponding cotetrad field e^a_α using the components of \bar{h}^α_β and h^α_β in x^α :

$$e_a^\alpha(x) = (\bar{h}^\alpha_0(x), \bar{h}^\alpha_1(x), \bar{h}^\alpha_2(x), \bar{h}^\alpha_3(x)) \quad (\text{A2})$$

and

$$e^a_\alpha(x) = (h^0_\alpha(x), h^1_\alpha(x), h^2_\alpha(x), h^3_\alpha(x)) \quad (\text{A3})$$

This tetrad induces a Lorentz metric on \mathbb{M} given by

$$\overset{\circ}{g}_{\alpha\beta} = e^a_\alpha \overset{\circ}{g}_{ab} e^b_\beta \quad (\text{A4})$$

where $\overset{\circ}{g}_{ab} = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$ are components of $\overset{\circ}{g}_{\alpha\beta}$ in the tetrad basis. Since $\eta_{\alpha\beta}(x) = \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$, equation (A4) is mathematically the same as equation (23) in chart x^α . Therefore $\overset{\circ}{g}_{\alpha\beta} = g_{\alpha\beta}$ and we can rewrite equation (A4) as

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = e^a_\alpha g_{ab} e^b_\beta \quad (\text{A5})$$

The Weitzenböck connection corresponding to the tetrad e_a^α in the Weitzenböck gauge is:

$$\overset{\circ}{\Gamma}^\alpha_{\beta\gamma} = e_a^\alpha e^a_{\beta,\gamma} \quad (\text{A6})$$

This equation is mathematically identical to equation (A1) in x^α . Therefore, $\overset{\circ}{\Gamma}^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}$ is a Weitzenböck connection.

Appendix B: Newtonian Limit

We recover the Newtonian limit of the theory in two stages. In the first stage, let us obtain the Newtonian equation of motion of a particle from the geodesic equation. Consider an isolated system of non-relativistic particles in a weak gravitational field (with gravitational potential $\ll 1$), for example, the solar system. For this system, we choose a chart $x^\alpha = (t, x, y, z) = (t, x^i)$ in which,

$$\eta_{\alpha\beta} \approx \text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1) \quad (\text{B1})$$

$$h^\alpha_\beta = \delta^\alpha_\beta + f^\alpha_\beta \quad (\text{B2})$$

with

$$|f^\alpha_\beta| \ll 1$$

so that

$$\bar{h}^\alpha_\beta \approx \delta^\alpha_\beta - f^\alpha_\beta \quad (\text{B3})$$

Since the matter action S_ψ obeys the equivalence principle, a free particle moves along a geodesic $x_p^\alpha = (t, x_p^i)$ of the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ given by,

$$\frac{d^2 x_p^\alpha}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma(g)^\alpha_{\beta\gamma} \frac{dx_p^\beta}{d\tau} \frac{dx_p^\gamma}{d\tau} = 0 \quad (\text{B4})$$

where $d\tau = \sqrt{-g_{\alpha\beta} dx_p^\alpha dx_p^\beta}$ and $\Gamma(g)^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}$ is the Levi-Civita connection of $g_{\alpha\beta}$. Since the particle is moving slowly,

$$\frac{dx_p^i}{d\tau} \ll \frac{dt}{d\tau} \quad (\text{B5})$$

Substituting equations (B1)–(B3) in (23) and (24) and retaining terms up to first order in f^α_β , we obtain:

$$g_{\alpha\beta} \approx \eta_{\alpha\beta} + 2 f^\gamma_{(\alpha} \eta_{\beta)\gamma} \quad (\text{B6})$$

$$g^{\alpha\beta} \approx \bar{\eta}^{\alpha\beta} - 2 f^{(\alpha}{}_\gamma \bar{\eta}^{\beta)\gamma} \quad (\text{B7})$$

so that

$$\frac{\partial g_{00}}{\partial x^i} \approx -2 \frac{\partial f^0_0}{\partial x^i} \quad (\text{B8})$$

For non-relativistic sources, the contribution from time derivative of gravitational potential is negligible compared to that from spatial derivatives,

$$\frac{\partial g_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial t} \ll \frac{\partial g_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x^i} \quad (\text{B9})$$

Using relations (B5)–(B9), we simplify the geodesic equation (B4) and retain terms up to first order in f^α_β to obtain,

$$\frac{d^2 t}{d\tau^2} = 0 \quad (\text{B10})$$

$$\frac{d^2 x_p^i}{dt^2} = -\nabla^i f^0_0 \quad (\text{B11})$$

where $\nabla^i = \bar{\eta}^{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}$ is the gradient operator. Equation (B11) is the Newtonian equation of motion of a particle with f^0_0 identified as the Newtonian gravitational potential.

Now, in the second stage, let us obtain the Newtonian field equation of f^0_0 from the field equations of h^α_β . For later convenience, we multiply the field equations (39) by $(2c_1 + c_2 + 3c_3) \delta^\mu_\alpha \delta^\nu_\beta - c_3 g^{\mu\nu} g_{\alpha\beta}$ to obtain,

$$(2c_1 + c_2 + 3c_3) \mathcal{G}^{(\mu\nu)} - c_3 g^{\mu\nu} \mathcal{G} = 8\pi G ((2c_1 + c_2 + 3c_3) T^{\mu\nu} - c_3 g^{\mu\nu} T) \quad (\text{B12})$$

where $\mathcal{G} = g_{\alpha\beta} \mathcal{G}^{\alpha\beta}$ and $T = g_{\alpha\beta} T^{\alpha\beta}$.

The energy-momentum tensor of non-relativistic sources with rest mass density ρ is

$$T^{\mu\nu} \approx \text{diag}(\rho, 0, 0, 0) \quad (\text{B13})$$

We substitute this and the approximations (B1)–(B3) in the 00–component of equation (B12) and retain terms up to first order in $f^\alpha{}_\beta$ to obtain,

$$\nabla^2 f^0{}_0 \approx \alpha (4\pi G \rho) \quad (\text{B14})$$

with

$$\alpha = -\frac{2(2c_1 + c_2 + 2c_3)}{(2c_1 + c_2)(2c_1 + c_2 + 3c_3)} \quad (\text{B15})$$

where $\nabla^2 = \bar{\eta}^{ij} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^i \partial x^j}$ is the Laplacian operator. Equation (B14) reduces to the desired Newtonian field equation of $f^0{}_0$ when $\alpha = 1$ or equivalently,

$$2c_1 + c_2 = -1 - \frac{3}{2}c_3 \pm \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{9c_3^2 - 4c_3 + 4} \quad \forall c_3 \in \mathbb{R} \quad (\text{B16})$$

provided $2c_1 + c_2 \notin \{0, -2c_3, -3c_3\}$

Specifically for $c_3 = 1$, we obtain $2c_1 + c_2 \in \{-1, -4\}$ so that $\alpha = 1$.

In the special case $(2c_1 + c_2, c_3) = (-1, 1)$, equations (B12) simplify to the trace reversed form,

$$\mathcal{G}^{(\mu\nu)} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu} \mathcal{G} = 8\pi G \left(T^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu} T \right) \quad (\text{B17})$$

Appendix C: Schwarzschild Solution

Let the spacetime manifold $(\mathbb{M}, \eta_{\alpha\beta}, h^\alpha{}_\beta)$ of an isolated, static, spherical object of mass M be a nonempty open subset of Minkowski manifold $(\mathbb{R}^4, \eta_{\alpha\beta})$ with $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ being the gravitational field of the mass M . We assume that the physical metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$ is static and spherically symmetric with respect to M . This means that \mathbb{M} admits the spherical Schwarzschild chart (t, r, θ, ϕ) in which $g_{\alpha\beta}$ takes the standard diagonal form $g_{\alpha\beta} = \text{diag}(g_{00}(r), g_{11}(r), r^2, r^2 \sin^2 \theta)$.

Since $\mathbb{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^4$, the corresponding Cartesian Schwarzschild chart (t, x, y, z) is globally defined. Therefore, $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ has the canonical form $\eta_{\alpha\beta} = \text{diag}(-1, 1, r^2, r^2 \sin^2 \theta)$.

We further assume that $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ is static (invariant under time reversal), parity even (invariant under reflection) and spherically symmetric with respect to M . Therefore, it has the general form $h^\alpha{}_\beta = \text{diag}(h^0{}_0(r), h^1{}_1(r), 1, 1)$.

For the special case $(2c_1 + c_2, c_3) = (-1, 1)$, the field equations (39)–(41) yield the Schwarzschild solution:

$$h^\alpha{}_\beta = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C1})$$

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} -\left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2 \sin^2 \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C2})$$

where $r_s = 2GM$ is the Schwarzschild radius.

$h^\alpha{}_\beta$ is singular at $r = r_s$. This is a true singularity; the Lagrangian $\frac{\mathcal{L}_h}{\sqrt{|g|}}$, a scalar invariant, is singular at $r = r_s$. In addition, $h^\alpha{}_\beta$ is imaginary in the region $r < r_s$. Therefore, the Schwarzschild solution is valid only in the region $r > r_s$.

In order to obtain the conserved total energy and total momentum using equation (56), we need to integrate over both the boundaries of this region, one at $r = r_s$ and the other at $r = \infty$. The calculations yield

$$P_\mu = \begin{bmatrix} M \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C3})$$

Using equation (55) leads to the same result.

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